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Biomass-dispersal trade-off and biodiversity

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1
2 **1 Abstract**

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4 2 Production-diversity patterns lack a single explanation fully integrated in theoretical
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6 3 ecology. An ecological state equation has recently been found for ruderal vegetation. We
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8 4 studied 1649 plots from twenty-nine ecological assemblages and analyzed the
9
10 5 relationship between diversity, biomass and dispersal looking for a pattern across these
11
12 6 ecosystems. We found that high biomass and low dispersal values were significantly
13
14 7 associated with high diversity plots under stationary conditions, and vice versa,
15
16 8 involving a biomass-dispersal trade-off that is coherent with well-established ecological
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18 9 principles. Therefore, energy, estimated as one half of the product of biomass and square
19
20 10 dispersal, can only reach its maximum at intermediate levels of diversity. This explains
21
22 11 the well-know humped relationship between production and diversity. We also explore
23
24 12 why the rest of the diversity-production patterns can be explained starting from
25
26 13 disruptions of this basic pattern. Simultaneously, the product of diversity, biomass and
27
28 14 square dispersal is equal to the ecological equivalent of the Boltzmann's constant
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30 15 included in the ecological state equation that remains valid for all the assemblages
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32 16 explored due to scale variations in the value of the above-mentioned constant. Hence,
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34 17 biomass-dispersal trade-off explains production-diversity patterns and the ecological
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36 18 state equation in simultaneous agreement with conventional ecology and physics.
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48 20 **Keywords:** biomass-dispersal trade-off; production-diversity patterns; *r-K* selection
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50 21 theory; species diversity; ecological Boltzmann's constant; ecological state equation.
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1. Introduction

The relationship between species diversity and ecosystem functioning is one of the most important points for ecosystems conservation (Tilman, 1999; Hector et al., 2001; Willig, 2011). For instance, diversity and trophic production can be associated according to the following patterns: a) a unimodal hump-backed curve (e.g. Chase and Ryberg, 2004; Graham and Duda, 2011); b) direct linear (e.g. Marquard et al., 2009; Li et al., 2012); c) inverse linear (e.g. Moser and Hansen, 2009); there may also be d) no evidence of any significant relationship (Huston et al., 2000; Long and Shaw, 2010), or even more than one of these patterns can emerge for a single taxocene depending on the observation scale (Zhang and Wang, 2012). The proportions of these four patterns according to a survey of the ecological literature including a total of 200 cases (Waide et al., 1999) are 30%, 26%, 12% and 32% respectively.

Such a variety of patterns may be due to: (i) the absence of simple laws at the biological community level (Lawton, 1999; Simberloff, 2004); (ii) the spurious influence of variables not explicitly included in the analysis (Mouquet et al., 2002; Hawkins et al., 2003; Mittelbach et al., 2003); or (iii) methodological issues (Huston, 1997; Naeem and Wright, 2003; Gamfeldt and Hillebrand, 2008).

Alternatives (ii) and (iii) may share a common cause due to the use of surrogate indicators instead of direct measurements. For example, the number of species (richness) is frequently assumed to be a good indicator of diversity, on the one hand, and biomass a good measure of production on the other. However, this procedure to evaluate production-diversity patterns has been questioned (Whittaker and Heegaard, 2003; Dangles and Malmqvist, 2004; Wilsey et al., 2005).

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2 1 According to the conventional concept of biological diversity (Magurran 2004, p. 17),
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4 2 the assumption that richness can replace diversity leaves evenness (i.e. the relative
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6 3 abundance between species) out of the analysis. Similarly, the assumption that biomass
7
8 4 can replace production neglects the fact that production is the flow of energy that
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10 5 sustains standing biomass (Odum, 1968; 1969).

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13 6 On the other hand, an ecological state equation (ESE, Eq. (7), below), similar to the
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15 7 ideal gas state equation, has recently been found for ruderal vegetation (Rodríguez et al.,
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17 8 2012). In comparison with the well-consolidated theory regarding the thermodynamic
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19 9 nature of the ecosystem (Odum, 1968; 1969), the ESE is, for the moment, an empirical
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21 10 result restricted to a particular kind of ecological assemblage. Thus, three main issues
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23 11 should be clarified: Can it be assumed that the ESE is a general pattern under stationary
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25 12 conditions (SC)? What is the ecological foundation of this equation? Is there any reliable
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27 13 reason to consider this equation as unconnected from the conventional ecological theory?
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32 14 In this article, we develop an all-encompassing explanation of the above-mentioned
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34 15 issues that becomes a general exploration of the functional meaning of species diversity
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36 16 including several new findings. With such a goal, we examine the relationship between
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38 17 diversity and a proxy for trophic production calculated in a similar way to that of kinetic
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40 18 energy in physics. As a result, we found a biomass-dispersal trade-off (B-DT) that
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42 19 explains production-diversity patterns in agreement with conventional ecology and
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44 20 physics. We also obtained a general validation of the ESE for all the stationary systems
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46 21 sampled, confirming at the same time the congruence of this equation with well-
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48 22 established ecological principles. Finally, we discuss the general meaning of these
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50 23 findings.
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2. Material and methods

2.1. Indicators

a) Species diversity per plot (Shannon, 1948; Magurran, 2004):

$$H_p = - \sum_{i=1}^S \frac{n_i}{N_p} \ln \frac{n_i}{N_p} \quad (1)$$

where S : species number per plot; n_i : number of individuals or colony elements (e.g. corallites) of species i ; N_p : total number of individuals per plot = $\sum n_i$.

b) Total biomass per plot (m_{eTp}) and mean individual biomass per plot (m_e) in kg: biomass has been recognized as one the most important indicators to describe ecological dynamics at any hierarchical level (e.g. Margalef, 1963; Odum, 1969; Bombelli et al., 2009).

c) Ergodic (transitivity or meaning equivalence between space and time from the analytical point of view, see Appendix A, pp. 1-3) indicator of dispersal activity (Rodríguez et al., 2012):

$$I_e = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^S (I_{ei,j})}{S} \quad (2)$$

$$I_{ei,j} = \left(\frac{d_{i,j}}{\sigma_{i,j}} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$d_{i,j} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m \left(\left(\sqrt{(x_j - x_k)^2 + (y_j - y_k)^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{2i_{j,k}}{i_j + i_k} \right) \right)}{m} \quad (4)$$

where $d_{i,j}$ is the mean dispersal activity of a species i in plot j with central geographic coordinates (x, y) within a total space s_0 divided into m plots; i_j and i_k are the respective abundances of i in plots j and k ; $i_{j,k}$ is the shared number of individuals of i in plots j and

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 2 1 k (e.g. if $j = 7$ and $k = 12$, then $i_{j,k} = 7$); $(2i_{j,k})/(i_j + i_k)$ is the Bray-Curtis similarity index
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 4 2 (Washington, 1984) which functions in a similar way to a relative probability (it is
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 6 3 ranged from 0 to 1 with 1 value if $i_j/i_k = i_k/i_j = 1$); $\sigma_{i,j}$ is the standard deviation of $d_{i,j}$; $I_{ei,j}$
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 9 4 is the ergodic indicator of dispersal activity of a species i in plot j ; I_e is the ergodic
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 11 5 indicator of dispersal activity of the species group in plot j ; and S is the species number
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 13 6 in plot j . $\sqrt{((x_j - x_k)^2 + (y_j - y_k)^2)}$ is the Pythagorean theorem that allows the estimation (see
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 15 7 Eq. (4)) of a mean Euclidean distance adjusted for the degree of quantitative similitude
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 17 8 of the distribution of species between plots ($(2i_{j,k})/(i_j + i_k)$). In other words, if $(2i_{j,k}/i_j + i_k)$
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 19 9 = 1 the estimated distance remains unchanged, but it is proportionally shorter as $(2i_{j,k}/i_j +$
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 21 10 $i_k) < 1$. The more heterogeneous the distribution of this adjusted distance, the lower the
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 23 11 dispersal. Hence Eq. (3) is the reciprocal of the coefficient of variation of Eq. (4). Lastly,
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 25 12 the final assessment of dispersal activity per plot is the mean value of Eq. (3) regarding
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 27 13 all the species per plot (Eq. (2)). For additional details about Eq. (2) see Appendix A.

33 14 d) Total eco-kinetic energy per plot:

$$36 15 E_{eTp} = N_p E_e = N_p (1/2 m_e \cdot I_e^2) = 1/2 m_{eTp} \cdot I_e^2 \quad (5)$$

38 16 where E_e is the mean eco-kinetic energy per individual per plot.

41 17 Eq. (5) reflects that part of the energy captured by organisms is converted into
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 43 18 biomass (m_e), and another part is invested in dispersal (I_e) via reproduction coupled with
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 45 19 individual movement (non-sessile animals), or emission of propagules and vegetative
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 47 20 reproduction (in sessile organisms). Eq. (5) assumes that trophic energy can be estimated
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 49 21 in a similar way as mechanical kinetic energy ($E = 1/2 m \cdot v^2$, where m = physical mass, v =
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 51 22 velocity and $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{s}^2 = \text{Joule, J}$) is calculated in the case of any other body, from atoms
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 53 23 to galaxies (Resnick et al., 2001). Therefore, there is no reason to suppose that an
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 55 24 equation similar to E cannot be equally useful in the case of ecosystems, mainly if we

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2 1 accept the equivalence and free transformation of all kinds of energy (First Law of
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4 2 Thermodynamics). The quantitative proportionality between E , E_{eTp} and trophic energy
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6 3 is an ulterior goal that depends on finding, previously, a reliable ecological meaning for
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9 4 the relationship between E_{eTp} and H_p .

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11 5 The orthodox way to evaluate the amount of trophic energy in ecosystem depends on
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13 6 measuring the primary production (the balance of photosynthetic CO_2 assimilation with
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16 7 photorespiratory CO_2 release) expressed in $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ (e.g. Gilpin et al., 2002). The
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18 8 exact measurement of this parameter has become very complex (e.g. Corno et al., 2005,
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21 9 Beardall et al. 2009), almost as a little science in itself whose resulting data are
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23 10 sometimes difficult to interpret (e.g. Chapin et al., 2006) and cannot inform us about the
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26 11 amount of energy at a small-scale or disaggregated level as in the case of eco-kinetic
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28 12 energy assessments (e.g. total energy / species / plot or mean energy / individual /
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31 13 species / plot). On the contrary, one of the main methodological advantages of
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33 14 calculating Eq. (5) is that it does not require any special device or adjustment, but the
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36 15 data can be directly obtained from the conventional sampling procedure applied in the
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38 16 standard biotic community studies.

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40 17 Eq. (5) does not indicate the energetic balance of a given organism, evaluating this is
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42 18 neither a goal nor an element of our proposal. The understanding of the meaning of this
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44 19 decision requires several physical and statistical details. In the first place, if the system is
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46 20 under stationary conditions (balance between inputs and outputs or null net exchange
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48 21 with its surroundings; the ecological state equation –Eq. (7), below– should yield an
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51 22 equality only under such circumstances), then the individuals of the system neither gain
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54 23 nor lose energy at the large scale; consequently, the study of the energetic balance of a
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1 given organism means nothing by definition from the statistical viewpoint applied in our
2 approach.
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4 Secondly, the thermostatistical degrees of freedom (t.d.f.) are three general ways in
5 which a given molecule can fix energy: rotational motion; internal vibration motion
6 between the atoms of the molecule and; finally, the translational linear motion of the
7 molecule as a whole. Only the last t.d.f. contributes to our physical notion of temperature
8 (Roller and Blum, 1986; Aguilar, 2001; Resnick et al., 2001). Our proposal assumes an
9 approximated equivalence between individuals and molecules to extend the classical
10 formalism from physics to ecosystem ecology. Consequently, only the translational
11 motion at the plot level statistically assessed by means of I_e matters within our model.

12 The internal energy embodied in the living tissues of any organism is neglected since
13 it is assumed to be equivalent to those internal degrees of freedom of a molecule that do
14 not contribute to temperature and, therefore, their implication to perform a given
15 ecological work can be neglected for our purpose. Is it approximately in agreement with
16 reality this decision? Whales, elephants, walruses, crocodiles, whale sharks, moon fishes
17 and sequoia trees are, the most of them, very large organisms with a huge amount of
18 internal energy and a strong top-down ecological control, but not any of them is in the
19 bottom of any significant food chain. Contrarily, several of these species are in danger of
20 extinction due to human consumption and, in contrast, our farms are full of animals and
21 plants that, even in nature, are smaller than the former species in individual size but
22 more abundant and with a higher capability of dispersal and population replacement.
23 This indicates something that is well-known in ecology: abundance and dispersal matter.

24 e) Ecological equivalent (k_e , Rodríguez et al., 2012) of the Boltzmann constant (k_B
= 1.3806504E-23 J/molecule/K):

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 2 1 $k_e = [2N_p(1/2m_e I_e^2) \cdot H_p] / N_p \rightarrow$ statistically constant for all the plots under SC (6)
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4 2 In the case of ruderal vegetation $k_e \approx 1.3806504E+02$ J_e·nat/individual; where J_e:
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 6 3 ecoJoule (kg·d²); d: dispersal unit (the unit of expression of Eq. (2)); nat: the unit of
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 9 4 expression of Eq. (1) when natural logarithms are used.

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 11 5 Eq. (6) indicates the amount by which individual energy fluctuates with a change of
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 13 6 species diversity of one nat/individual at the plot level. According to Rodríguez *et al.*
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 15 7 (2012) the key factor for the detection of stationarity is that k_e maintains, in the mean,
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 17 8 the same value for all the plots included in the ecological assemblage explored. In other
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 19 9 words, k_e is the conversion factor between total biomass (m_{eTp}) and square dispersal (I_e^2),
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 21 10 placed on the left of the ESE (Eq. (7)), and individual abundance (N_p) and diversity per
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 23 11 plot (H_p), placed on the right of the equation:
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 28 12 $2N_p(1/2m_e I_e^2) = N_p k_e / H_p$ or $2(1/2m_{eTp} I_e^2) = N_p k_e / H_p$ or $2E_{eTp} = N_p k_e / H_p$ (7)
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 30

31 13 Eq. (7) is very similar to the ideal gas state equation ($PV = nRT = n(R/N_A)T = Nk_B T =$
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 33 14 $Nmv_x^2 = 2N(1/2mv_x^2)$, –Tipler and Mosca, 2010, pp. 570-575, Eq. (17.7) to (17.12) and
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 35 15 Eq. (17.16) to (17.18)–, where P : pressure, V : volume, n : number of moles, R : universal
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 37 16 constant of gases (the increment of kinetic energy per mole per Kelvin), T : absolute
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 39 17 temperature, N_A : Avogadro’s number (the number of molecules in a mole), k_B :
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 41 18 Boltzmann’s constant (the increment of kinetic energy per translational degree of
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 43 19 freedom per molecule per Kelvin), N : number of molecules, m : molecular mass, v_x^2 :
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 45 20 mean square molecular velocity along the x axis = $1/3v^2$ and v^2 : mean square molecular
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 48 21 velocity regarding 3D space). Appendix A includes further comments about the
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 51 22 underlying assumptions in Eq. (7).
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2.2. Hypothesis

Under SC, biomass (m_e or m_{eTp}) and H_p are positively correlated, whereas square dispersal (I_e^2) and H_p are negatively correlated. This combination of correlations sets plots with high biomass and low dispersal at high diversity values and plots with an inverse combination of biomass, dispersal and H_p values at the opposite end of the diversity gradient (B-DT).

2.3. Consequences of the hypothesis

Consequence 1: E_{eTp} (Eq. (5)) decreases at very low diversity values due to the reduced values of biomass (m_e or m_{eTp}). E_{eTp} is also depleted at very high diversity values due to the low values of dispersal (I_e^2). Therefore, $E_{eTp} = 1/2 m_{eTp} I_e^2$ (total eco-kinetic energy per plot assumed as a proxy for trophic energy) only can reach its maximum value at intermediate diversity levels (hump-backed diversity-production curve). The rest of the diversity-production patterns can be explained starting from disruptions of this basic pattern.

Consequence 2: B-DT is coherent with three well-known ecological regularities: a) Cope's rule (Cope, 1896; Kingsolver and Pfennig, 2004; Hone et al., 2005): there is a positive relationship between increased individual size of new species added to ecosystems during times of stability which promotes diversity (edge of high diversity and high biomass within B-DT). b) Rapoport's rule: at the hemisphere level, species dispersal (I_e , in this article) is reduced, promoting coexistence, as latitude descends towards communities of greater diversity (Rapoport, 1975; Stevens, 1989). This rule can act locally (Rohde, 1996; Hernández et al., 2005), which is coherent with the opposite correlation between I_e^2 and H_p embraced by a BD-T. c) r - K selection theory (MacArthur and Wilson, 1967; Pianka, 1970; Reznick et al., 2002): r -species tend to be small in

1 individual size and with a high rate of reproduction and dispersal in micro and macro-
2 environments of low diversity values. K -species are typical of the opposite ecological
3 condition. Consequently, r - K selection theory is a sort of combination between
4 Rapoport's rule and Cope's rule and it is also equivalent to the hypothetical B-DT as a
5 whole.

6 Consequence 3: Simplifying Eq. (6) with a *didactic intention*, we obtain:

$$7 \quad k_e = [2N_p(\frac{1}{2}m_e I_e^2) \cdot H_p] / N_p = (N_p \cdot m_e \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p) / N_p = (m_{eTp} \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p) / N_p = m_e \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p \quad (8)$$

8 Thus, deriving a rational inference (\therefore = therefore) symbolically represented in terms
9 of alternatives (\vee = or) and fluctuations direction ($\downarrow \uparrow$) in reference to a given ecological
10 assemblage:

$$11 \quad (\text{biomass} \uparrow, I_e^2 \downarrow, H_p \uparrow) \vee (\text{biomass} \downarrow, I_e^2 \uparrow, H_p \downarrow) \therefore m_e \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p = k_e \rightarrow \text{constant} \quad (9)$$

12 Eq. (9) is the main ecological foundation of Eq. (7) given that k_e is a sort of "hinge"
13 or switch factor between the right and the left side of the equality in the ESE.

14 15 2.4. Statistical procedures

16 I_e^2 , m_e and m_{eTp} were correlated with H_p (diversity per plot) using Pearson's
17 correlation coefficient (r) and the correlative relationship between these indicators was
18 graphically analyzed by means of the spline-fit (piecewise cubic polynomial
19 interpolation) curves of both sets of correlations with regard to the whole group of
20 ecological assemblages ordinally ranked according to their taxonomic resemblance and
21 temporal sequence.

22 Cover percentage is considered a good proxy for biomass (e.g. Röttgermann et al.,
23 2000; Muukkonen et al., 2006). Therefore, the correlation between cover (mean cover
24 per species per plot, c_e , and total cover per plot, c_{eT}) and H_p replaced the correlation

1 between biomass and H_p due to the absence of biomass values in one (code: pf, see
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3
4 below) of the twelve kinds of assemblages included in our study.

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6 The value of k_e (Eq. (6)) was calculated for all the plots per assemblage. The
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8 difference between the observed mean value of the ecological equivalent of the
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10 Boltzmann's constant ($k_{e(o)}$) and the respective expected value ($k_{e(e)}$) was tested by means
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12 of the t -test for a single sample to verify if the ESE (Eq. (7)) was also valid for other
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14 cases besides ruderal vegetation. Collaterally, we also assessed the difference between
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16 the mean values of the two members of the ESE by using either the t -test for dependent
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18 samples or the t -test for unequal samples sizes in those cases in which $N_p k_{e(e)}/H_p$ was
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20 undefined due to $H_p = 0$.

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22 The statistical standardization of i data (i – mean/standard deviation) allows
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24 comparison of the slopes of correlations calculated from variables expressed in different
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26 units. Thus, the absolute difference between the values of β (regression coefficient) of
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28 the standardized values of I_e^2 and biomass with regard to H_p was correlated with the p -
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30 value (significance level) of the difference between $k_{e(o)}$ and $k_{e(e)}$ to explore the influence
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32 of the balance between the dispersal gradient and the biomass gradient on ecological
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34 stationarity.

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36 The total eco-kinetic energy per plot (E_{eTp} , Eq. (5)) was graphically related with H_p
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38 and its maximum values for each $\Delta H_p = 0.1$ nat/individual were adjusted by means of
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40 polynomial equations to highlight the presumptive hump-backed diversity-production
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42 curve in those assemblages under SC. This analysis also supported our interpretation
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44 about the rest of the patterns as contingent disruptions of the hump-backed diversity-
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46 production curve. Data from comparable assemblages with a similar range of H_p values
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2 1 were included in the same graph. Statistica-6 (StatSoft Inc., 2001) was used for all the
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4 2 statistical tests.

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6 3 All the values of the main indicators for the statistical procedures applied to each
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9 4 ecological assemblage are included in Appendix B. All the graphical results from
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11 5 correlations and hypothesis tests per ecological assemblage are also included in
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13 6 Appendix B.

14 15 16 7 17 18 8 *2.5. Samplings*

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21 9 The statistical procedures described above were applied to data from the following
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23 10 kinds of ecological assemblages:

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26 11 Marine microalgae; marine interstitial meiofauna of sandy beaches; massive (non-
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28 12 branching) corals; litter invertebrates in subtropical laurel and Canarian pine forest;
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31 13 tropical rocky shore snails; coral reef fishes; ruderal vegetation; Mediterranean shrub
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33 14 vegetation; mixed shrub vegetation; coastal succulent shrub vegetation and pine forest
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35
36 15 vegetation. The sampling method and data processing for each one of these assemblages
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38 16 are explained in Appendix A.

39 40 41 17 42 43 18 **3. Results**

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45 19 The whole group of assemblages included a wide range of values (Table 1) with
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48 20 regard to number of plots (from 12 to 219); total number of individuals (from 160 to
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50 21 2.06E+07); bi- or tri-dimensional space (volume) per plot (from 0.000001 m³ to 10000
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52 22 m²); population density (from 0.51 ind. m⁻² to 4.68E+11 ind. m⁻³); mean distance
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54 23 between plots (from 4.64 m to 29259 m); species richness (from 11 to 239); species
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57 24 diversity (from 0.85 nat/individual to 3.56 nat/individual) as well as mean individual
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1 biomass per plot (from 5.53E-14 kg to 5.02 kg). Therefore, any regular pattern derived
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4 from these data would suggest independence of scale or taxon.
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6 The main general pattern that we obtained deserves particular attention (Table 2): one
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8
9 hundred percent of negative correlations (and 82.76%, 24 of 29, were significant)
10
11 between square dispersal (I_e^2) and species diversity (H_p) matched with positive
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13 correlations between biomass (either m_e or m_{eTp}) and H_p (85.18%, 23 of 27, were
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15 significant, or almost significant: ma3).
16
17

18 An auxiliary graph (Fig.1) helps to illustrate the pattern: the spline fits of r -values for
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20 dispersal vs. diversity and biomass vs. diversity are mirror images of each other ($r =$
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22 -0.644 , $p = 0.0003$ between the set of r -values of I_e^2 vs. H_p and the respective r -values
23
24 of biomass vs. H_p). Any displacement of the correlation between I_e^2 and H_p towards
25
26 negative and significant r -values matched with an opposite movement of the respective
27
28 correlation between biomass (either m_e or m_{eTp}) and H_p . There were exceptions to this
29
30 pattern: *i*) mf2, in which there was a negative and significant correlation between m_{eTp}
31
32 and H_p ($r = -0.31$, $p = 0.019$) combined with a low and non-significant correlation
33
34 between I_e^2 and H_p ($r = -0.08$, $p = 0.56$) and *ii*) the segment from rv5 to rv7 whose low
35
36 and non-significant correlations between I_e^2 and H_p were combined with a trend to
37
38 positive correlations between biomass and H_p that were estimated for rv6 and rv7 by
39
40 means of the interpolation of the sequence of data from the same place. These
41
42 exceptions were cases without stationarity (see comments below).
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50 In all of the cases in which the above-mentioned pattern was found, there was no
51
52 significant difference (Table 2) between the observed and the expected value of $k_e(p)$
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54 nor between the left and the right side of the ESE (p').
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1 Rsn1 was the most typical isolated example of this previous combination of
2 conditions ($r: H_p, I_e^2 = -0.91, p < 0.001$; $r: H_p, m_{eTp} = +0.64, p = 0.013$; $k_{e(o)}=1.37$ vs.
3 $k_{e(e)} = 1.38, p = 0.977$; $2E_{eTp}$ vs. $N_p k_{e(e)}/H_p, p' = 0.91$).

4 Additionally, all the assemblages adjusted to this combination showed a clear trend to
5 a humped relationship between the total eco-kinetic energy per plot (E_{eTp} , Eq. (5)) and
6 species diversity (Fig. 2, panels a-j).

7 Panels k and l (Fig. 2) show the most remarkable differences in comparison with the
8 stationary hump-backed pattern. Coincidentally, these two cases also showed the most
9 significant differences between $k_{e(o)}$ and $k_{e(e)}$ (see the p values for mf2 and rv5, Table 2)
10 as well as between the two sides of Eq. (7) (see the respective p' values for mf2 and rv5,
11 Table 2). On the one hand, the key factor in mf2 seems to be the space without E_{eTp}
12 observations in the lower left corner of panel k in Fig. 2 due to the lack of biomass
13 limitation despite the reduction of H_p ($r = -0.31, p = 0.019$). This explains the left shift in
14 maximum value of total eco-kinetic energy.

15 On the other hand, the key factor in rv5 is the space without observations in the lower
16 right corner of panel l in Fig. 2, due to the lack of significant limitation for dispersal
17 despite the increase of H_p ($r = -0.17, p = 0.223$) combined with the expected increase of
18 biomass ($r = 0.50, p < 0.001$). This explains the trend of the maximum value of total
19 eco-kinetic energy to the right extreme of H_p values.

20 The correlation between the absolute difference of the slopes ($Abs\beta_{Ie}-\beta_{me}$) of the
21 standardized values of dispersal and biomass with regard to species diversity and the p -
22 value of the comparison between $k_{e(o)}$ and $k_{e(e)}$ was negative and significant ($r = -0.409, p$
23 $= 0.048$). Thus, less difference between slopes tends to be associated to higher equality
24 between the observed and the expected value of k_e even if such a result depends only on

1 three observations out of stationarity (mif2, rv5 and rv4 to a lesser extent) given that
2 under SC the absence of correlation ($r = -0.091$, $p = 0.694$) between $\text{Abs}\beta_{I_e-\beta_{m_e}}$ and $p_{k_{e(o)}}$
3 vs. $k_{e(e)}$ was the expected.

4 **4. Discussion**

6 In summary, a gradient of increasing species diversity per plot under SC was
7 associated with: *i*) reduction of dispersal activity and *ii*) increase in biomass either at the
8 individual (m_e) or the plot (m_{eTp}) level. Therefore, any stationary gradient of species
9 diversity can also be assumed to be a gradient of *r-K* selection whose internal changes
10 are quantified in terms of a given scale value of k_e . Such a B-DT leads directly to a
11 humped pattern of the total energy per plot, because at both ends of H there is a shortage
12 of one of the two parameters needed for the growth of E_{eTp} ($E_{eTp} = \frac{1}{2}m_{eTp} \cdot I_e^2$). Recent
13 evidence suggests that this pattern could even apply on a global scale: the gradient of
14 productivity associated with the latitudinal gradient of species diversity peaks between
15 30° and 50° latitude (Huston and Wolverton, 2009). In other words, the most productive
16 ecosystems in each hemisphere are not located equatorially (usually very diverse) or
17 near the poles (usually with low diversity), but rather at mid-latitudes.

18 The above-discussed results indicate that our hypothesis as well as its three main
19 consequences is difficult to reject.

20 The opposite correlation between $\text{Abs}\beta_{I_e-\beta_{m_e}}$ and p from $k_{e(o)}$ vs. $k_{e(e)}$ is an additional
21 factor that supports the influence of the balance between dispersal and biomass to
22 sustain the humpbacked pattern between E_{eTp} and H_p . For instance, there were no
23 significant p values either for I_e vs. H_p or m_e vs. H_p in Ms (Table 2), but the r -values for

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2 1 I_e and m_e were very similar; this seems to be sufficient to produce a typical stationary
3
4 2 state (see the hump-backed shape of the scatter in panel i, Fig. 2).
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6 3 The maximum power principle states that “*during self-organization, system designs*
7
8
9 4 *develop and prevail that maximizes power intake, energy transformation, and those uses*
10
11 5 *that reinforce production and efficiency*” (Odum, 1995, p. 311; see also Hall, 2004).
12

13 6 Therefore, the most parsimonious option is to assume that mf2 (panel k, Fig. 2) is
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15 7 drifting to the right edge of the species diversity spectrum; on the contrary, rv5 (panel l,
16
17 8 Fig. 2) is drifting to the opposite position.
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19

20 9 Summarizing, stationarity is supported by a maximum value of energy per plot placed
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22 10 at intermediate diversity values (hump-backed pattern); if this maximum is displaced to
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24 11 the left (panel k in Fig. 2: negative linear correlation pattern between total energy and
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26 12 species diversity) it pulls the whole system towards lower diversity values where energy
27
28 13 maximum is more probable, and vice versa (panel l in Fig. 2: positive linear correlation
29
30 14 trend between the total energy per plot and species diversity).
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34 15 Stationarity means constancy of internal energy (gains balanced by losses) at the
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36 16 system level. So, if we establish a net consumption relationship with any ecosystem that
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38 17 spontaneously tends to stationarity, it will eventually be extinguished, since a net energy
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40 18 gain is only possible out of stationarity. Correspondingly, non-stationarity is a transition
41
42 19 stage in which the system either gains or loses energy in its movement from one
43
44 20 stationary state to another.
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48 21 Two additional elements support this approach:
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50 22 a) In regard to mf2 (panel k, Fig. 2), the regression equation between $k_{e(o)}$ and H_p is
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52 23
$$k_{e(o)} = 1.406E-5 + 2.371E-05 \cdot H_p \quad (r = 0.452, p < 0.001)$$
 where the intercept
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56 24 $1.406E-5 \rightarrow 1.380650E-5 \text{ J}\cdot\text{e}\cdot\text{nat}/\text{individual}$. This equation seems to indicate that
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2 1 the non-stationary assemblage mf2 is moving towards the left edge of the
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4 2 diversity gradient, starting from a previously stationary state in which $k_{e(o)} \approx$
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6 3 $1.3806504E-4$ (as in mf1 and mf3, see Table 2), to reach an ulterior stationary
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8 4 state with a different maximum power position at a lower H_p value in which $k_{e(o)} \approx$
9
10 5 $1.3806504E-5$ $J_e \cdot \text{nat}/\text{individual}$.

11
12
13
14 6 b) With regard to rv5 (panel 1, Fig. 2) the monthly sequence of the total number of
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16 7 individuals per assemblage (N_a) in the same place from rv1 to rv9 ($308 \rightarrow 319 \rightarrow$
17
18 8 $193 \rightarrow 406 \rightarrow 160 \rightarrow 23055 \rightarrow 19805 \rightarrow 2618 \rightarrow 1995$) indicates that in rv6 (N_a
19
20 9 $= 23055$) and rv7 ($N_a = 19805$) there must have been a substantial increase in
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22 10 biomass per plot (m_{eTp}). However, the correlation between I_e^2 and H_p for rv6 and
23
24 11 rv7 does not correspond to what would be expected according to dispersal-
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26 12 biomass trade-off (see $r: H_p, I_e^2$ and its p -value for rv6 and rv7, Table 2). Thus, in
27
28 13 rv6 and rv7, biomass per plot increased with no reduction of I_e^2 , so positive
29
30 14 displacement from stationarity towards greater H_p values of the ecosystem as a
31
32 15 whole in these two assemblages indicates a breach of the dispersal-biomass trade-
33
34 16 off due to increased net energy input to the ecosystem (see the fit segments for
35
36 17 dispersal and biomass from rv5 to rv7, Fig. 1). In such circumstances the
37
38 18 observed pattern of total energy per plot is not unimodal and humped for
39
40 19 intermediate values of H_p , but direct and linear due to a net increase of E_{eTp} in the
41
42 20 right edge of H_p , similarly to the right half of panel 1 in Fig. 2. Consequently, rv5
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44 21 can be assumed to be a “sprout” of successional change towards new positions of
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46 22 higher diversity (rv6 and rv7) in which the new energy maximum of a subsequent
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48 23 stationary state will be located.
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1 This does not mean that there is a pre-eminence of maximum energy per plot over
2 species diversity or vice versa. On the contrary, it is a question of “tuning” between the
3 biological community and its environment. When the supply of energy from the
4 environment is reduced, the maximum value of internal total energy per plot moves
5 towards lower diversity values, in which *r*-selection prevails, and vice versa (increased
6 net supply of energy from outside → “tuning” of the ecosystem at high diversity per plot
7 values, where *K*-selection prevails). As a result, there should be a direct correlation
8 between the mean value of species diversity per plot and the value of species diversity
9 where maximum energy is reached (Fig. 3a).

10 On the other hand, the movement of maximum energy towards higher diversity
11 values does not mean that a stationary ecosystem of high diversity has a higher
12 availability of energy per unit of biomass. A physical body at rest ($v = 0$) has physical
13 mass (m) and potential energy, but it has no available kinetic energy ($\frac{1}{2}m \cdot 0^2 = 0$) to
14 perform any physical work. Similarly, a species i present only in one ($I_{e,i,j} = 0$) or very
15 few plots ($I_{e,i,j} \rightarrow 0$) has biomass and potential energy (the energy chemically embodied
16 in its living tissues from an initial photosynthetic transduction of light energy into
17 chemical energy) but, due to its low level of replication in space and time, has
18 insufficient eco-kinetic energy ($n_i \frac{1}{2} m_e I_{e,i,j}^2 \rightarrow 0$) to support any kind of intense trophic
19 exploitation due to its low capability for population replacement.

20 Such species (with large biomass and low $I_{e,i,j}$) are frequent in high-diversity
21 communities. Therefore, there should be an opposite correlation between the availability
22 of energy per unit of biomass per plot ($E_{eTp}/m_{eTp} = \frac{1}{2} N_p m_e I_e^2 / N_p m_e \propto \frac{1}{2} I_e^2$) and species
23 diversity (Fig. 3b). This is in agreement with a very old classical statement on the
24 reduction of productivity expressed in terms of the energy/biomass ratio or turnover rate

1 (Margalef, 1963) or, conversely, the gain of efficiency expressed in terms of the
2 biomass/energy ratio (Odum, 1969) in those communities in which species diversity is
3 high.

4 In a mixture of several gases in equilibrium (that is to say, species under stationary
5 conditions in our analytical context), the molecules with higher mass (m) move at lower
6 mean square speed (v^2) and those with lower mass move faster (thus $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 \approx \text{constant}$,
7 in the mean, per molecule per cell of phase space for all the concurrent gases). This is
8 the simplest expression of the principle of equipartition of energy between t.d.f. (Roller
9 and Blum, 1986, p. 699; Aguilar, 2001, p. 567; Tipler and Mosca, 2010, p. 577).

10 Similarly, in the sampled ecosystems, “heavier” plots (which accumulate more m_{eTp})
11 tend to have lower values of I_e^2 ; conversely, “lighter” plots tend to have higher values of
12 I_e^2 . Thus solar energy, for the whole ecosystem and under stationary conditions, tends to
13 be equally invested at the “macroscopic” level between alternative ecological d.f.
14 (internal energy embodied in biomass vs. dispersal), in an approximately consistent way
15 with a sort of principle of trophodynamic equipartition on a large scale.

16 However, there is an internal gradient on a “microscopic” level because the micro-
17 associations of species are not randomly distributed (as it happens with molecules in the
18 gas phase space): those plots with a combination of heavier species and less dispersal are
19 concentrated in a stable way at the high end of species diversity, meanwhile the plots
20 with lighter species combinations and greater dispersal tend to be at the low end. This is
21 perhaps the main pro-functional gradient or thermodynamic constraint to avoid chaos
22 and ecological degradation under far from equilibrium stationary conditions.

23 Therefore, Eq. (9) indicates a peculiarity of the ecosystem in comparison with gases:
24 in the latter case molecular mass is constant for each kind of gas regardless of kinetic

1 energy even at the individual level; but in the case of ecosystem this is not even true for
2 individuals that belong to the same species. Therefore, if we would rewrite Eq. (9) in a
3 comparative way for two masses of the same type of substance in equilibrium at
4 different temperatures (T), then we would establish the following didactic expression
5 (m_c : constant molecular mass of the substance; v_x : mean molecular velocity along the x
6 axis):

$$(m_c, v_x^2 \uparrow, T \uparrow) \vee (m_c, v_x^2 \downarrow, T \downarrow) \therefore m_c \cdot v_x^2 / T = k_B \rightarrow \text{constant} \quad (10)$$

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8
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10 The noticeable difference between Eq. (9) and Eq. (10) indicates that the slow down
11 process (I_e reduction) from low to high diversity values is an essential feature that
12 distinguishes the ecosystem from the non-living physical systems and it can be assumed
13 as the “source” of biomass increment either from the ontogenetic or phylogenetic point
14 of view. This trend towards larger sizes can be related to the less expensive energetic
15 maintenance per gram of biomass under high diversity conditions (see Fig. 3b).

16 Thus, maximum productivity depends on those non-stationary systems (with quasi-
17 continuous growth) of low diversity that can support intense trophic exploitation, as in
18 the case of agroecosystems. Alternatively, high diversity communities have lower
19 productivity but higher efficiency (a greater amount of biomass supported per unit of
20 energy: m_{eTp}/E_{eTp} ratio). This compensatory relationship between productivity and
21 efficiency depends on the correlative position of dispersal and biomass in the above-
22 commented ratios (dispersal is part of the numerator and biomass part of the
23 denominator to estimate productivity, and vice versa to assess efficiency). As a result, a
24 primary B-DT implies a secondary trade-off between productivity and efficiency.

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2 1 Additionally, items a) and b) indicate that the time trend of an ecological assemblage
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4 2 can be glimpsed by means of a momentary observation of the spatial pattern of an
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6 3 ecosystem (ergodicity, see comments about Eq. (2) in Appendix A, pp. 1-3).
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9 4 In summary, our proposal is congruent with the opinion of Willig (2011, p. 1710):
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11 5 *“the absence of a modal [hump-backed] pattern suggests the absence of defining trade-*
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13 6 *offs. Finally, for a modal pattern to emerge, the trade-offs must be strong and*
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15 7 *pervasive.”*
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21 9 **5. Concluding remarks**

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24 10 Our proposal opens a new branch or family of models for ecological modelling based
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26 11 on an affirmative answer to a question that is fundamental to understand ecosystem
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28 12 functioning from the physics perspective. Can we describe ecosystem functioning
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30 13 under stationary conditions by means of the orthodox models developed by the
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32 14 conventional thermodynamics and thermostatics?; our proposal responds
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34 15 affirmatively to this questions since the *stationary* ecological state is consistent with the
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36 16 formal definition of equilibrium state as the pivotal concept of thermodynamics and
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38 17 thermostatics: *“By definition (...) thermodynamics describes only static states of*
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40 18 *macroscopic systems”* (Callen, 1985, p. 6), (...) *“in all systems there is a tendency to*
41
42 19 *evolve toward states in which the properties are determined by intrinsic factors and not*
43
44 20 *by previously applied external influences. Such simple terminal states are, by definition,*
45
46 21 *time independent. They are called equilibrium states”* (Callen, 1985, p. 13). The values
47
48 22 of state variables do not change with time neither under equilibrium nor under
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50 23 stationarity. That is to say, the stationary state is for the analysis of open systems what
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52 24 equilibrium state is for the analysis of isolated systems (Montero and Morán, 1992).
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2 1 Additionally, such classical models were conceived for systems of weakly interacting
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4 2 elements and, accordingly, a reduction in the strength of interactions with the increase of
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6 3 diversity is an essential requirement to maintain community stability (Margalef, 1974, p.
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8 4 366; McCann et al., 1998; Neutel et al., 2002; Banašek-Richter et al., 2009). In
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10 5 agreement with the former, the general ecological trends along non-stationary transitions
11
12 6 could be deduced by comparison between different stationary states or by means of a
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14 7 harmonious arrangement between the outcomes derived from our proposal and the
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16 8 results obtained from those approaches that, implicitly, are based on a negative response
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18 9 to the question above outlined or are independent of this question (e.g. those models
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20 10 intended to describe non-stationary ecological states).

21
22 11 According to our results, Eq. (7) is more than a particular case restricted to ruderal
23
24 12 vegetation. An additional key element in comparison with Rodríguez *et al.* (2012) is that
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26 13 $k_{e(e)} = 1.3806504E\varphi$ with $\varphi = -x_i, \dots, 0, \dots, +x_i$, where x_i is an integer number that tends to
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28 14 be typical of each particular kind of ecological assemblage, e.g. $x_i = -10$ from ma1 to
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30 15 ma4 (marine microalgae); $x_i = 00$ from rsn1 to rsn3 (tropical rocky shore snails) or $x_i =$
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32 16 +02 from rv1 to rv9 (ruderal vegetation). This implies that the ESE is valid (as a pattern)
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34 17 regardless of environment, body size or taxon because the mantissa of $k_{e(e)}$ (1.3806504)
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36 18 is the same for all ecological assemblages under SC but φ varies following a suitable
37
38 19 scale progression according to variation of ecological conditions.

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40
41 20 Three main general positions can be assumed about this subject:

- 42
43 21 1) Very pessimistic and conservative position: these findings are circumstantial. This
44
45 22 is the typical case of a fluke in which an improbable combination of coincidences
46
47 23 emerges when exploring one scientific field by using tools from another field.

48
49 24 There are two main facts to take into account regarding this position: a) all our

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2 1 foundational knowledge about ecosystem functioning is based on

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4 2 thermodynamics rather than on “classical” ecology itself. b) “...in the history of

5
6 3 *human thinking the most fruitful development frequently take place at those points*

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8 4 *where two different lines of thought meet*” (Heisenberg, 2000, p. 129).

9
10
11 5 2) Moderately optimistic position: This approach is simply a mathematical artifact

12
13 6 whose main instrumental contribution is a better understanding of the underlying

14
15 7 patterns in ecosystem functioning. In this case our proposal is congruent with the

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17 8 ultimate purpose of science itself: to gain understanding of the natural world

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19 9 (Oreskes, 2003).

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23 10 3) Optimistic position: This model shows internal consistency and reflects a natural

24
25 11 reality. In this case, this article suggests some answers but, at the same time, it

26
27 12 poses many new questions (e.g. What is the cause of the discrete or discontinuous

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29 13 scale variation in the value of k_e between successive stationary states?; Are there

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31 14 underlying principles connected with B-DT that can be useful to explain species

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33 15 coexistence issues, for instance, the old controversy between competitive

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35 16 exclusion and functional redundancy (see Lewin, 1983)?; What are the

36
37 17 advantages, disadvantages and epistemological limits of the models based on

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39 18 physics to explain ecosystem functioning?). This would be the best alternative,

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41 19 since any reliable answers to these new questions hold promise of probable new

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43 20 findings, and this is an essential goal of science.

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49 21 Nevertheless, one of the main values of this approach lies in logical transitivity: our

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51 22 results indicate that A (ecological state equation) is consistent with B (biomass-dispersal

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53 23 trade-off) and B is consistent with C (conventional ecology; i.e. Cope’s rule, Rapoport’s

1 rule, r - K selection theory, production-diversity patterns and productivity-efficiency

2 trade-off). As a consequence, A is also consistent with C .

3

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2 **1 Figure captions**

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4 **2 Fig. 1.** Relationship between the correlations I_e^2 vs. H_p , and biomass (m_e or m_{eTp}) vs. H_p ,
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7 **3** for all the ecological assemblages. Equivalent graphs for the rest of indicators in Table 2
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9 **4** are unsuitable due to large scale differences even for a single indicator. max.:
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12 **5** maximum. *Non-significant p -value of r . Ecological assemblage codes in Table 1.

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14 **6**
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16 **7 Fig. 2.** E_{eTp} vs. H_p . (a) ma1-ma4₍₂₎. (b) mf1 and mf3. (c) cor₍₁₎. (d) lli. (e) pli₍₂₎. (f) rsn1-
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19 **8** rsn3. (g) crf. (h) rv1-rv4 and rv8-rv9. (i) Ms. (j) mxs' and css₍₁₎. (k) mif2. (l) rv5₍₁₎. Gray
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21 **9** lines represent polynomial equations that fit the maximum values of E_{eTp} per interval of
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24 **10** 0.1nat/individual in H_p (equations list in Appendix A). E_{eTp} is on the right axis in panel k
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26 **11** and left axis for $k_{e(o)}$ ($r = 0.452$, $p < 0.001$, regression equation –black fit line–: $k_{e(o)} =$
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29 **12** $1.406E-05 + 2.371E-05 \cdot H_p$; intercept indicated by an arrow) has been added to support
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31 **13** an analysis below. Sub-indexes between parentheses indicate the number of outliers
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34 **14** excluded from the fit.

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36 **15**
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38 **16 Fig. 3.** Relationship between energy indicators at the plot level and species diversity.
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41 **17** (a) Correlation between the value of diversity per plot in which the maximum value of
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43 **18** the total energy ($E_{eTp \text{ max.}}$) is reached and the general mean value of species diversity per
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46 **19** plot. (b) Correlation between the mean value of available energy per unit of biomass per
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48 **20** plot (E_{eTp}/m_{eTp}) and the total species diversity of each assemblage (H_T).
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Biomass-dispersal trade-off and biodiversity

Fig. 1.

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Fig. 2.

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Fig. 3.

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Table 1

General ecological indicators of each ecological assemblage (A_e)*

A_e	n_p	N_a	s_{0p}	$d = N_a / (s_{0p} n_p)$	d_{mp}	S	H_T	m_e
ma1	35	1.241E+07	0.000001 ⁽³⁾	3.55E+11	5.04	55	2.209	5.53E-14
ma2	43	1.833E+07	0.000001 ⁽³⁾	4.26E+11	5.11	57	2.037	5.82E-14
ma3	45	1.710E+07	0.000001 ⁽³⁾	3.80E+11	5.32	54	2.193	6.50E-14
ma4	44	2.059E+07	0.000001 ⁽³⁾	4.68E+11	5.11	62	2.194	6.48E-14
mif1	40	4360	0.00032 ⁽³⁾	3.41E+05	13.33	79	2.487	2.81E-08
mif2	56	19034	0.00032 ⁽³⁾	1.06E+06	19.99	60	1.521	1.24E-08
mif3	51	34143	0.00032 ⁽³⁾	2.09E+06	16.99	137	2.744	1.58E-08
cor	71	1.951E+07	10	2.75E+04	29.38	19	1.795	3.21E-05
lli	193	11854	0.25	245.68	35.02	239	3.355	1.49E-04
pli	115	608	0.25	21.15	34.06	98	3.262	1.34E-04
rsn1	14	1531	1	109.36	4.64	23	2.292	1.54E-03
rsn2	15	949	1	63.27	4.64	21	1.580	9.71E-04
rsn3	12	1094	1	91.17	4.64	17	1.489	5.95E-04
crf	72	7062	40 ⁽³⁾	4.98	29.38	58	2.354	4.10E-02
rv1	59	319	4	1.35	30.05	24	2.335	4.01E-02
rv2	59	323	4	1.37	30.05	26	2.360	4.48E-02
rv3	56	192	4	0.86	30.05	19	2.251	8.81E-02
rv4	59	412	4	1.75	30.05	28	2.404	4.81E-02
rv5	54	160	4	0.74	30.05	20	2.435	6.07E-02
rv6	60	23055	4	96.06	30.05	41	2.166	
rv7	60	19805	4	82.52	30.05	83	2.841	
rv8	60	2618	4	10.91	30.05	57	1.707	2.97E-02
rv9	60	2117	4	8.82	30.05	29	1.255	3.94E-02
Ms	28	664726	10000	2.37	5656.51	37	2.760	5.16E-01
mxs	19	2725	100	1.43	29259.23	77	3.557	
mxs'	19	962	100	0.51	29259.23	27	2.807	5.02E+00
pf1	17	1293	100	0.76	18413.55	53	2.711	
pf2	219		100		8897.14	63	0.847	
css	14	1110	100	0.79	267.596	11	1.661	2.58E+00

* n_p : number of plots. N : total number of individuals per assemblage. s_{0p} : space per plot in m^2 or m^3 ⁽³⁾. d : population density per space unit per plot. d_{mp} : mean distance between plots in meters. S : total species richness. H_T : total species diversity (Eq. (1) calculated in regard to the whole assemblage) in nat/individual. m_e : mean individual biomass per plot in kg. ma: marine microalgae. mif: marine interstitial meiofauna of sandy beaches. cor: massive (non-branching) corals. lli and pli: litter invertebrates in laurisilva and pine forest, respectively. rsn: tropical rocky shore snails. crf: coral reef fishes. rv: ruderal vegetation. Ms: Mediterranean shrub vegetation. mxs: mixed shrub vegetation. pf: pine forest vegetation. css: coastal succulent shrub vegetation.

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Table 2

Combinations of correlations (r) that support biomass-dispersal trade-off and significance level (p) of the t -test between the observed ($_{(o)}$) and the expected ($_{(e)}$) value of k_e as well as (p') between the left ($2E_{eTp}$) and the right ($N_p k_{e(e)}/H_p$) side of the ecological state equation (Eq. (7)).[†]

A_e	$r: H_p, I_e^2$	$r: H_p, m_e$	$r: H_p, m_{eTp}$	$k_{e(o)}$	$k_{e(e)}$	p	p'
ma1	-0.38 , 0.023	0.37 , 0.027	0.18, 0.299 ₍₁₎	1.72E-10	1.38E-10	0.106	0.672
ma2	-0.44 , 0.003	0.64 , <0.001	0.25, 0.107	1.74E-10	1.38E-10	0.099	0.142
ma3	-0.31 , 0.036	0.29 , 0.058	0.01, 0.966	1.78E-10	1.38E-10	0.136	0.188
ma4	-0.41 , 0.006	0.35 , 0.021	0.19, 0.226 ₍₁₎	1.65E-10	1.38E-10	0.288	0.261
mif1	-0.49 , 0.001	0.44 , 0.005 ₍₂₎	0.16, 0.311	1.56E-04	1.38E-04	0.417	0.855
mif2	-0.08 , 0.561	-0.03, 0.832	-0.31 , 0.019	3.93E-05	1.38E-05	3E-15	2E-10
mif3	-0.45 , <0.001	0.35 , 0.012	-0.03, 0.861	1.65E-04	1.38E-04	0.066	0.508
cor	-0.31 , 0.009 ₍₁₎	0.04, 0.738	0.54 , <0.001 ₍₂₎	1.67E-01	1.38E-01	0.228	0.658
lli	-0.23 , 0.002 ₍₁₎	-0.02, 0.837	0.23 , 0.002	1.36E+00	1.38E+00	0.834	0.496
pli	-0.33 , <0.001	-0.01, 0.912	0.56 , <0.001 ₍₁₎	1.35E-01	1.38E-01	0.825	0.164
rsn1	-0.91 , <0.001	0.33, 0.251	0.64 , 0.013	1.37E+00	1.38E+00	0.977	0.910
rsn2	-0.71 , 0.003	0.58 , 0.023	0.49, 0.0609	1.44E+00	1.38E+00	0.863	0.099
rsn3	-0.76 , 0.004	-0.64, 0.026	0.72 , 0.0080	1.40E+00	1.38E+00	0.945	0.416
crf	-0.39 , <0.001	0.38 , 0.001 ₍₁₎	-0.02, 0.874	1.50E+02	1.38E+02	0.671	0.125
rv1	-0.39 , 0.002	0.32, 0.014	0.67 , <0.001	1.36E+02	1.38E+02	0.848	0.822
rv2	-0.45 , <0.001	0.22, 0.097	0.63 , <0.001	1.39E+02	1.38E+02	0.969	0.652
rv3	-0.30 , 0.024	-0.19, 0.152 ₍₁₎	0.32 , 0.016 ₍₁₎	1.45E+02	1.38E+02	0.557	0.744
rv4	-0.44 , <0.001	0.06, 0.675	0.22 , 0.096	2.73E+02	1.38E+02	0.004	0.028
rv5	-0.17 , 0.223	-0.09, 0.514	0.52 , <0.001	6.94E+01	1.38E+02	2E-13	9E-11
rv6	-0.05 , 0.692 ₍₁₎						
rv7	-0.09 , 0.519						
rv8	-0.52 , <0.001	0.48 , <0.001	0.40, 0.002	1.55E+02	1.38E+02	0.113	0.880
rv9	-0.51 , <0.001	0.35 , 0.007 ₍₁₎	0.24, 0.062	2.00E+02	1.38E+02	0.173	0.323
Ms	-0.11 , 0.582	-0.30, 0.115	0.10 , 0.598	1.58E+03	1.38E+03	0.611	0.420
mxs	-0.47 , 0.042	0.62, 0.005	0.73 , <0.001				
mxs'	-0.47 , 0.049 ₍₁₎	0.56, 0.013	0.60 , 0.006	1.48E+04	1.38E+04	0.844	0.827
pf1	-0.84 , <0.001	-0.55, 0.024	0.63 , 0.007				
pf2	-0.43 , <0.001	-0.32, <0.001 ₍₁₎	0.48 , <0.001				
css	-0.71 , 0.005	0.55 , 0.041	0.47, 0.091	1.23E+04	1.38E+04	0.633	0.416

[†]The first number in each correlations column is the value of r and the second (on the right of the comma) is the respective p value. Sub-indexes between parentheses indicate the number of outliers excluded from the respective correlation. Biomass data were replaced by a proxy (cover) in mxs, pf1 and pf2. rv6 and rv7 lack biomass values due to adverse weather conditions. The r -values used in Fig. 1 are highlighted in boldface. Appendix B includes the graphical analysis that support the main results included in Table 2 for each ecological assemblage.